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ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ**

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THE APPROACHES AND TECHNIQUES OF AUDIOLINGUAL AND DIRECT METHOD

ANNOTATION

Audiolingual Method (ALM) of the late 1940 and 1950s is considered as one of the best examples of periodical method. The ALM with its oral production drills is used almost half a century. Whereas, Direct Method started from behavioral theories of learning of the time. The approaches and techniques in the language teaching profession have stressed the importance of self – esteem, motivation, students cooperatively learning together, developing individual strategies for constructing meaning focused on the communicative process in language learning. Keep on reading for all the details it is essential to know about the most popular foreign language teaching methods. Some of the ones covered are the communicative approach, total physical response, the direct method, task-based language learning, suggestopedia, grammar-translation, the audio-lingual approach and more.

Key words: approach, technique, audio-lingual method, direct Method, self – esteem, individual strategies, communicative process, situational contexts, communicative approach, total physical response, grammar-translation, audio-lingual approach.

ПОДХОДЫ И ТЕХНИКИ АУДИОЛИНГВАЛЬНОГО И ПРЯМОГО МЕТОДА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Аудиолингвальный метод (АЛМ) конца 1940-х и 1950-х годов считается одним из лучших примеров периодического метода. АЛМ с его сверлами для орального производства используется почти полвека. Принимая во внимание, что прямой метод начался с поведенческих теорий обучения того времени. Подходы и методы в профессии преподавателя языка подчеркивают важность самооценки, мотивации, совместного обучения студентов, разработки индивидуальных стратегий построения смысла, ориентированных на коммуникативный процесс при изучении языка. Продолжая читать, вы узнаете все подробности о самых популярных методах преподавания иностранного языка. Некоторые из них включают коммуникативный подход, тотальную физическую реакцию, прямой метод, изучение языка на основе задач, суггестопедию, грамматический перевод, аудиолингвальный подход и многое другое.

Ключевые слова: подход, техника, аудиолингвальный метод, прямой метод, самооценка, индивидуальные стратегии, коммуникативный процесс, ситуационные контексты, коммуникативный подход, общефизическая реакция, грамматика-перевод, аудиолингвальный подход.

AUDIO-LINGVAL VA DIREKT METODGA YONDASHUV VA TEXNIKALAR

ANNOTATSIYA

1940-1950-yillarning oxiri va 1950-yillardagi Audiolingual Metod (ALM) davriy metodning eng yaxshi namunalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Og'zaki nutqni o'stiruvchi mashqlar ALM deyarli yarim asrdan beri ishlatilgan. To'g'ridan-to'g'ri usul o'sha davrni o'rganishning xulq-atvor nazariyalaridan boshlangan. Til o'qituvchisi kasbidagi yondashuv va uslublari o'z-o'zini hurmat qilish, motivatsiya, o'quvchilarni birgalikda o'rganish, til o'rganishda kommunikativ jarayonga yo'naltirilgan ma'noni yaratish uchun individual strategiyalarni ishlab chiqish muhimligini ta'kidladi. Chet tilini o'rgatishning eng mashhur usullari haqida barcha tafsilotlarni bilish uchun o'qishda davom eting. Ulardan ba'zilari kommunikativ yondashuv, umumiy jismoniy javob, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri usul, vazifaga asoslangan til o'rganish, taklifopediya, grammatik tarjima, audiolingual yondashuv va boshqalarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: yondashuv, texnika, audio-lingual usul, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri usul, o'z-o'zini hurmat qilish, individual strategiyalar, kommunikativ jarayon, vaziyat konteksti, kommunikativ yondashuv, umumiy jismoniy javob, grammatika-tarjima, audio-lingual yondashuv.

Teaching a foreign language to students may be a difficult but rewarding task that provides them with completely new avenues for communication. It is advantageous for teachers to be familiar with the many different language-learning methodologies, including ESL teaching strategies, so they may be adaptable with their lesson plans as necessary.

For all the information you need to know about the most common techniques for teaching foreign languages, keep reading. The communicative approach, entire physical response, direct technique, task-based language acquisition, suggestopedia, grammar-translation, audio-lingual approach, and others are among those that are discussed.

The Direct Method encourages learners to think in the target language by having all instruction take place in that language. The student does not translate or speak in their original tongue in class. This approach's proponents think that students should study a second language independently of their mother tongue.

Grammar is not explicitly taught by instructors; rather, it is indirectly taught by induction. This implies that by using the language, learners learn grammar rules on their own. Students are expected to establish links between their experiences and their language. They achieve this by emphasizing correct pronunciation and the improvement of oral abilities.

Direct Method (2)

Features:

- Meaning conveyed through demonstration “see-hear-say”
- Teacher replaces book as the model
- Accuracy in speaking & writing emphasized
- Speech dominates over writing
- Immersion in the target language
- Teaching through target language
- Grammar learnt inductively from examples
- Use of visual aids

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Our kids’ comprehension, fluency, reading, and listening abilities are all enhanced by this technique. For this form of language acquisition, common tactics include discussion, reading aloud, writing, and student self-correction. There are different ways of assessing learners’ knowledge and skills. They are held for different purposes whether for measuring proficiency, diagnosing learners’ strengths and weaknesses, placing learners into different levels of a course or for other reasons [2].

The Audio-Lingual Method promotes students to form linguistic learning habits. Pattern drills, particularly dialogues that the teacher utilizes to assist pupils’ practice and memorize the language are the main way that students learn. These conversations adhere to established communication patterns.

There are four types of dialogues utilized in this method:

- Repetition, in which the pupil precisely repeats the teacher’s words
- Inflection, where a word changes from its previous sentence’s form (for instance, a word can go from the singular to the plural).
- Replacement, which includes changing a word while keeping the rest of the sentence’s structure the same.
- Restatement, in which the student reformulates the teacher’s statement.

This technique gets its name from the order in which language skills are taught. It begins with listening and speaking, followed by reading and writing. That is, the emphasis is on listening and speaking the language before experiencing the written form. For this reason, in his TESOL method, teachers use only the target language within the classroom. Many of today’s online language learning apps and programs strictly follow the spoken language approach to language teaching. This is a good option for remote and/or solo language learning, even if it is his traditional ESL teaching method. As a result of such efforts, fields such as linguistics, cognitive linguistics, ethnolinguistics, psycholinguistics, ethnopsycholinguistics, and pragmalinguistics are developing and these fields are gaining importance because they approach language as a phenomenon in constant movement, growth and change, unlike traditional structuralism [3].

THE AUDIO LINGUAL METHOD

TECHNIQUES

- Dialogue memorization
- Backward buildup drill
- Use of minimal pairs
- Grammatical drills
- Vocabulary learning
- Quickly communicate

Structural approach Proponents of the structural approach understand language as a set of grammatical rules that must be learned sequentially in a specific order. The emphasis is on mastering these structures and building one skill on top of another, rather than memorizing vocabulary. This is similar to how young children learn new languages naturally. An example of a structural approach is to teach the present tense of verbs like "to be" before moving on to more advanced tenses like the present tense that uses "to be" as an auxiliary word. A structured approach teaches all four of her major language skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing. This is a technique that teachers can combine with a variety of other language teaching methods. Most of his ESL textbooks take this approach. Grammar concepts that are easier to understand are taught before more difficult ones.

It is clear that, the methods which were devised 40 or 50 years ago or so, are too constructive to apply to a wide range of learners in an enormous number of situational contexts. There is no quick and easy method that provides success. It is essential to analyze the difference between approach and method.

Critics of audio-lingual methodology were advocating more attention to rules and to the « cognitive code » of language. While in approach, teachers can choose particular designs and techniques for teaching a foreign language in a specific context.

Oral production drills can be a good example for audio-lingual method that leads learners to improve their speech habits. However, in the communicative approach, it is important to create an Information gap between speakers. Thus, the need to communicate is authentic because communication must take place to narrow the gap and accomplish the task. The task cannot be completed individually. Partners must work together to complete the assigned task successfully. The major difference between The Approaches and Techniques is in the functional purpose of language usage.

The Direct Method helps students obtain deeper insights in their discipline in the English language whereas the Audio-Lingual Method aims to achieve a high standard of everyday English skills including reading, writing, speaking, and listening across common areas of communication.

Moreover, the Audio-Lingual Method refers to formal English which teaches formal ways of speaking, writing such as those used in research papers.

It can be argued that, in the Direct Method one can face long and unfamiliar words, most of which have a specific or technical meaning.

The most distinctive features of the two types of approaches can be observed in the register of the language used in a course book. The results show that, it is essential to classify similarities and dissimilarities of different approaches in English language from the perspective of a graduate student and an EAP teacher. Having a clear understanding of what approaches and techniques of English language is like one can develop useful materials which will be helpful to learners. For instance, textbooks, research articles, essays and lectures are the significant resources to EAP learners in understanding The Approaches and Techniques of English Language.

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